

Infrared Spectral Studies of Calcium-Iron Hydroxylapatites

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The introduction of Fe²⁺ in calcium hydroxylapatite results in the formation of its solid solution. In the infra-red spectral studies of the samples the vibrations corresponding to ν_3 and ν_4 are shifted to lower frequencies due to an increase in mass and binding energy as a result of substitution of Ca²⁺ by Fe²⁺.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite which is also called bone mineral (CaHA), Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂, is the major inorganic crystalline component of human skeletal system^{1,2}. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions. Ca²⁺ → Fe²⁺ replacement reaction in CaHA is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of iron into human skeletal system according to the following equation :

As a part of series of physicochemical investigation on calcium-iron hydroxylapatites the present work is an attempt at the infrared spectral studies of these compounds.

Experimental

The details of preparation and characterisation of the samples were reported earlier³. The samples used for infrared studies were acetone washed and air dried. The i-r tracing was carried on Carl-Zeiss Jena UR 10 Double beam instrument in KBr mediums.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis by the method specially worked out⁴ are given in table 1. From

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM, IRON HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular Formulae	g atom ratio Ca+Fe/P
	Ca	Fe	P		
1.	39.84	-	18.52	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68
2.	34.96	6.01	18.21	Ca _{8.9} Fe _{1.1} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67
3.	27.01	15.50	17.71	Ca _{7.1} Fe _{2.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68
4.	18.44	25.75	17.15	Ca _{5.0} Fe _{5.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68
5.	11.05	34.69	16.71	Ca _{3.1} Fe _{6.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67
6.	3.57	43.79	16.23	Ca _{.0} Fe _{9.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68
7.	-	47.98	16.00	Fe ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68

the analytical data the molecular formula of each sample was calculated and the molar gram atomic ratios of $\frac{\text{Ca}+\text{Fe}}{\text{P}}$ of each of the sample was calculated

Fig. 1. IR traces of calcium-iron hydroxylapatites ! a, b, c, d, represents the spectra of sample nos. 1, 3, 5 and 7 respectively of table 1.

and found to have the value ~1.68 (theoretical 1.67). The i-r runs of a representative set of the samples. (Sl. No. 1, 3, 5, 7 of table 1) are given in fig. 1. The calcium hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with iron have hexagonal crystalline structure⁵ and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple

molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry. Tribasic phosphate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of T_d point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν_4 (570 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (1075 cm^{-1}) of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples (Fig. 1) it could be seen that the ν_3 and ν_4 frequencies corresponding to phosphate ion are shifted to lower frequencies and shape of the peaks was being effected by the introduction of Fe^{2+} into the samples. From the consideration of the peak shifts and alteration of peak length ratios one can infer that the phosphate structure is effected by the introduction of Fe^{2+} into the samples. The shift of the ν_3 and ν_4 of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass.

In Barnes expression⁶ $\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi c} \sqrt{\frac{K}{\mu}}$ which gives

a relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant the vibration frequency is dependent on the reduced mass μ of the participating atoms and the restoring forces K between atoms, all other terms remaining constant. When the equilibrium

distance between the positive and negative atoms of the molecule is decreased, K generally increases in the above equation. Substitution of Ca^{2+} with a nucleus like Fe^{2+} , gives rise to stronger coordination of the PO_4 group to the iron, through oxygen. This in turn weakens the P-O band, lowering K (increasing P-O band length) and the frequency is lowered. The PO_4^{3-} bending frequency is normally around $500\text{--}520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the bending modes do not shift very much under these conditions. But there the situation is more complex, presumably because of the splitting of the triply degenerate mode at 600 cm^{-1} and thus there is an increase from $520\text{--}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This theoretical explanation agrees well with the experimental data.

References

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